

REVIEW OF GENETIC RICKETS AND ITS CLASSIFICATION

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Annotation

Genetic rickets is a term used for definition of wide range of diseases caused by genetic changes with symptoms similar to nutritional vitamin D deficient rickets.

The etiology and pathogenesis somehow is different as genetic rickets can develop despite adequate intake of vitamin D and normal sun exposure. Hence, the diagnostics and therapy also differ a lot from of a nutritional rickets and require medical-genetic counseling, which includes not only management of a patient but also counseling the family for better planning of further child birth tactics.

Rickets is considered a severe disease if not treated adequately for a long time, with complications like bone deformation, bone and muscle pain, and a chronic vitamin D deficiency can lead to immunodeficiency, diabetes mellitus, heart and vascular system diseases, different types of cancer etc.

Genetic rickets can lead to even more severe consequences due to impaired metabolism of vitamin D, calcium and phosphates that can't be fixed just by adequate intake of vitamin D supplements and sun exposure, thus a long time treatment (usually lifelong) is required.

Nutritional rickets is considered to be mostly spread in developing countries where different conditions and lifestyles can decrease vitamin D, calcium and phosphorus intake and supplementation, shorten sun exposure. However, genetic rickets depends mostly on worldwide contribution level of corresponding genetic changes, being equally spread in developing and developed countries.

Although numerous types of genetic rickets have been established with causative genes revealed for most of them, no international consensus exists to current date on how to classify the genetic rickets.

This paper is a literature review of hereditary rickets' all known to date types, their epidemiology, causes, methods of diagnosing and differential diagnosing, methods of treatment. The purpose is to develop a full classification of genetic rickets based on etiology, pathogenesis and clinical manifestation. Such a classification can help to improve the diagnostics and management of genetic rickets.

Keywords: Rickets, genetic rickets, hereditary rickets, Vitamin D dependent rickets, Vitamin D resistant rickets, Hypophosphatemic rickets, Rickets-like diseases.

Introduction

Rickets is a medical condition in children, occurring because of bone remodeling disorder with material basis in impaired mineralization or calcification of growth plate and osteoid matrix before epiphyseal closure due to extreme and prolonged vitamin D deficiency or impaired homeostasis of vitamin D, calcium, phosphorus and magnesium due to rare inherited metabolic or hormonal disturbances, resulting in weak, softening bones prone to deformation. [1] [2] [3] [4] [5] [6] [7]

Signs and symptoms include following [2] [3] [5] [6] [7]: Bone pain or tenderness; bowed (curved) legs; large forehead; stunted growth; abnormally curved spine; large abdomen; abnormally shaped ribs and breastbone; wide wrist and elbow joints; teeth abnormalities

There is a huge number of genetic disorders with at least one of symptoms above, mentioned in literature as rickets – like diseases or diseases that should be differentially diagnosed from rickets: X-linked hypophosphatemic rickets (XLH), hypophosphatasia, achondroplasia, vitamin D-dependent rickets, pycnodysostosis and ectodermal dysplasia [8], renal diseases (renal osteodystrophy, Fanconi syndrome), tumor-induced osteomalacia, hypophosphatasia, McCune-Albright syndrome, and osteogenesis imperfecta with mineralization defect [9], genetic

disorders of vitamin D biosynthesis and action: vitamin D-dependent rickets type 1A (VDDR1A), 1B (VDDR1B), 2A (VDDR2A), and 2B (VDDR2B); genetic disorders of excessive renal phosphate loss (hereditary hypophosphatemic rickets) due to impairment in renal tubular phosphate reabsorption as a result of FGF23-related or FGF23-independent causes [10]

Materials and methods

A deep analysis of literature and genetic databases, such as OMIM, ClinVar, gnomAD, MedlinePlus, RareDiseases.org, MalaCards.org, GeneCards.org, for creating a full classification of hereditary rickets based on genetic reasons.

Pathogenesis of rickets

The primary absorption site for vitamin D is the jejunum. The 2 main sources of vitamin D in humans are vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol), produced by the skin after ultraviolet (UV) radiation (290-320nm)-dependent conversion of 7-dehydrocholesterol, and dietary intake of either vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol) or vitamin D₃. Both forms of vitamin D have identical biologic actions.

The initial step in the metabolic activation process is the introduction of a hydroxyl group at the side chain at C-25 by the hepatic enzyme, CYP 27 (a vitamin D-25-hydroxylase). The products of this reaction are 25-(OH)D₂ and 25-(OH)D₃, respectively. Further hydroxylation of these metabolites occurs in the mitochondria of kidney tissue, catalyzed by renal 25-hydroxyvitamin D-1 α -hydroxylase to produce 1 α ,25-(OH)₂ D₂ (activated vitamin D₂ or 1,25[OH]₂ D₂), the primary biologically active form of vitamin D₂, and 1 α ,25-(OH)₂ D₃ (calcitriol or 1,25[OH]₂ D₃), the biologically active form of vitamin D₃. [9]

The impairment in any stage of this metabolic chain can lead to vitamin D deficiency and rickets, which means that mutations in every gene coding any protein involved in vitamin D metabolism can be a reason of rickets – like disease. Hence,

Rickets should be differentially diagnosed from genetic rickets and many diseases that can have a clinical manifestation similar to rickets

Since the role of vitamin D deficiency in pathogenesis of nutritional rickets was established in 19th century, a lot of genetic reasons have been explored, as the methods of molecular biology has been improving, with new types and causative genes being discovered every year.

The prevalence of genetic rickets can be as much as 13% of all cases [11]

The increase of presence of codes for rickets with genetic reasons in ICD, which is a classification based primarily on etiologic factors, can be seen from ICD 9 to ICD 10 and ICD 11.

Only 4 codes for rickets (including nutritional) in ICD 9 (Version: 2009) [12].

Totally 10 codes for rickets and related disorders in ICD 10 (version: 2019) [13].

Totally 11 codes and 17 subcodes for rickets and related disorders in ICD 11 for mortality and morbidity statistics (version: 02/2022) [14].

Results

Types of rickets by genetic cause [15]

Vitamin D-related rickets

Vitamin D deficiency (due to malnutrition; rare mutations in *GC* - Vitamin D-Binding Protein; 7-dehydrocholesterol reductase - *DHCR7* and *CYP24A1* - Cytochrome P450, Family 24, Subfamily A, Polypeptide 1, or Vitamin D 24-Hydroxylase)

Vitamin D-dependent rickets (VDDR) or Vitamin D-pseudodeficiency rickets

Type 1: insufficiency in activation

VDDR1A: Hypocalcemic Vitamin D-dependent Rickets or 25-Hydroxyvitamin D3 1-alpha-hydroxylase deficiency (autosomal - recessive mutation of Cytochrome P450 Family 27 Subfamily B Member 1, *CYP27B1*)

VDDR1B: 25-OH hydroxylase deficiency (autosomal - recessive mutation of Cytochrome P450 Family 2 Subfamily R Member 1, CYP2R1)

Type 2: resistance to calcitriol

VDDR2A: calcitriol receptor mutation (autosomal-recessive mutation of Vitamin D Receptor, VDR)

VDDR2B: abnormal expression of a hormone response element-binding protein that interferes with the normal function of the vitamin D receptor (mutation of Prefoldin Subunit 4, PFDN4)

Type 3: excessive inactivation (autosomal – dominant mutation of Cytochrome P450 Family 3 Subfamily A Member 4, CYP3A4)

Hypophosphatemia-related rickets

Congenital

Vitamin D-resistant rickets (Hereditary hypophosphatemic rickets)

Autosomal dominant hypophosphatemic rickets (ADHR, autosomal-dominant mutation of Fibroblast Growth Factor 23, FGF23)

Autosomal recessive hypophosphatemic rickets 1 (ARHR1, autosomal recessive mutation of Dentin Matrix Acidic Phosphoprotein 1, DMP1) and 2 (ARHR2, autosomal recessive mutation of Ectonucleotide Pyrophosphatase/Phosphodiesterase 1, ENPP1)

X-linked dominant hypophosphatemic rickets (XLDHR, dominant mutation of Phosphate Regulating Endopeptidase Homolog X-Linked, PHEX)

X-linked recessive hypophosphatemic rickets (XLRHR, recessive mutation of Chloride Voltage-Gated Channel 5, CLCN5)

Hypophosphatemic Rickets with Hypercalciuria, Hereditary (autosomal-recessive mutation of Solute Carrier Family 34 Member 3, SLC34A3)

Hypophosphatemic Rickets and Hyperparathyroidism (autosomal-dominant mutation of gene called Hypophosphatemic Rickets And Hyperparathyroidism, HPRHP)

Secondary to other diseases

Secondary to malabsorption

Coeliac disease (genetically heterogeneous mutations of HLA-DQB1 - Major Histocompatibility Complex, Class II, DQ Beta 1)

Cystic fibrosis (autosomal – recessive mutation of CFTR - CF Transmembrane Conductance Regulator)

Crohn's disease (genetically heterogeneous mutations of NOD2 - Nucleotide Binding Oligomerization Domain Containing 2)

Disorders of calcium or phosphate excretion

Fanconi's syndrome, or Primary Fanconi renal tubular syndrome, which is related to Fanconi renal tubular syndrome 1 (autosomal dominant, or autosomal recessive mutation of GATM - Glycine Amidinotransferase)

Fanconi-Bickel syndrome (autosomal – recessive mutation of SLC2A2 - Solute Carrier Family 2 Member 2)

Low's Oculocerebrorenal Syndrome (X-linked recessive mutation of OCRL - Inositol Polyphosphate-5-Phosphatase)

Cystinosis (autosomal – recessive mutation of CTNS - Cystinosin, Lysosomal Cystine Transporter)

Hypoparathyroidism (genetically heterogeneous mutations of GCM2 - Glial Cells Missing Transcription Factor 2)

Achondroplasia or Hypochondroplasia (autosomal – dominant mutation of FGFR3 - Fibroblast Growth Factor Receptor 3)

Pycnodisostosis (autosomal – recessive mutation of CTSK - Cathepsin K)

Osteogenesis imperfecta (autosomal – dominant mutation of COL1A1 - Collagen Type I Alpha 1 Chain)

Tumor-induced osteomalacia (genetically heterogeneous mutations of FGF23 - Fibroblast Growth Factor 23)

Smith-Lemli-Opitz Syndrome (autosomal - recessive mutation of 7-dehydrocholesterol reductase - DHCR7, rs7944926, rs12785878 and rs11234027 – also associated with Vitamin D-dependent Rickets type 2b [16])

McCune-Albright syndrome (mosaicism of GNAS - GNAS Complex Locus)

Schimmelpenning-Feuerstein-Mims Syndrome, SFM (mosaicism of KRAS - KRAS Proto-Oncogene, GTPase)

Dent's disease type 1 (X-linked recessive mutation of CLCN5 - Chloride Voltage-Gated Channel 5)

Ectodermal dysplasia (genetically heterogeneous mutations of EDA - Ectodysplasin A)

Conclusions

Rickets and rickets-like diseases are a wide range of disorders that include over 30 nosology, each having its own causative gene. The full classification based on etiologic factor – a genetic reason, pathogenesis and clinical signs can help to better understand the diagnostics and management of this group of diseases. Mainly Rickets – like diseases can be divided into Vitamin D dependent and resistant forms, there are also a lot of conditions affecting skeletal system, but having no relation to vitamin D, Calcium and Phosphate metabolism. However this conditions can have a clinical manifestation similar to rickets and should be differentially diagnosed.

References

1. <https://disease-ontology.org/?id=DOID:10609>
2. <https://medlineplus.gov/ency/article/000344.htm>
3. <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/rickets/symptoms-causes/syc-20351943>
4. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rickets>
5. <https://meshb.nlm.nih.gov/record/ui?ui=D012279>
6. https://ncit.nci.nih.gov/ncitbrowser/ConceptReport.jsp?dictionary=NCI_Thesaurus&ns=ncit&code=C26878

7. Nutritional rickets: a review of disease burden, causes, diagnosis, prevention and treatment. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2019. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. file:///C:/Users/home/Downloads/9789241516587-eng.pdf
8. Rickets-like genetic diseases, MA Hong-Wei et al PMID: 24229581
9. Bone Mineralization and Related Disorders, Horacio B Plotkin et al
10. Genetic Causes of Rickets, J Clin Res Pediatr Endocrinol. doi: 10.4274/jcrpe.2017.S008
11. Incidence and prevalence of nutritional and hereditary rickets in southern Denmark, Signe Sparre Beck-Nielsen et al, DOI: 10.1530/EJE-08-0818
12. <http://icd9cm.chrisendres.com/index.php?srctype=diseases&srctext=rickets&Submit=Search&action=search>
13. <https://icd.who.int/browse10/2019/en#/E55.0>
14. <https://www.codingahead.com/disorders-of-metabolite-absorption-or-transport-definitions-icd-11-codes/>
15. <https://www.malacards.org/card/rickets?search=Rickets>
16. <https://diseases.jensenlab.org/Entity?documents=10&type1=9606&id1=ENSP00000347717&type2=-26&id2=DOID:0080887>
17. <https://icd.who.int/browse11/l-am/en#/http%3a%2f%2fid.who.int%2fid%2fentity%2f2047696084>